

A LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE EFFECTS OF ACTIVITY-BASED TEACHING METHOD ON LEARNING OUTCOMES

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Abstract

The paradigm shift in teaching strategy from teacher-centred to learner-centred instructional approach provide opportunity for research to identify novel ways of improving learning outcomes. This study reviewed related literature on the effects of activity-based teaching (ABT) method on learning outcomes at the primary school, junior secondary school and senior secondary school. Studies has shown that ABT method could enhance learning outcomes at the primary school level. However, a contradiction was discovered on the attitude of pupils taught Mathematics and those taught English with ABT method. The research findings shows that ABT method could enhance learning outcome of students in science subjects and social studies at both junior and senior secondary school level. Furthermore, this study discovered that there is no significant difference in the learning outcome of male and female students taught with ABT method at the senior secondary school level. Finally, it is recommended that authorities in education sector should support and encourage teachers to embrace the use of ABT method for teaching at the primary and secondary school levels.

Keywords: Literature Review, Activity-Based Method, Learning Outcomes, Students' Academic Achievement, Students' Academic Performance

Introduction

Activity Based teaching is a method in which students are engaged in the learning processes (Prince, 2004). In other word, Activity Based teaching strategy is the process in which students are actively involved in doing or in seeing something done. In this method, students learn by doing. It is employed when the teacher allows students to carry out a piece of work and learn at the same time. According to Quin (2012), activity-based teaching strategy includes a wide range of interesting activities, which is used sometimes interchangeably with terms like cooperative learning, collaborative learning, problem-based learning or inquiry based learning. It is typically defined as any educational strategy that engages students actively in the learning process. In Activity-based teaching method, students actively participate in the learning experience rather than being passive listeners.

In Activity Based instructional strategy, the teacher is a facilitator, motivator, guide and a coach not a sage on the stage (Stolen, 2009). In this method, the learner examines learning requirements and thinks on how to solve a problem at hand. The students do not learn about the content, rather they learn about the process to solve the problem. As they go

towards the solution of the problem, they also learn about the content (Churchill, 2013). In teaching students, the strategy that should be used should attempt to accommodate the diverse needs of the students in a class and allows for optimum learning by directly involving students. The main purpose of activity-based instructions in contrast to traditional teaching method is to change the focus from delivery of the content by the teacher to the students and active interaction (Kudryashova, Gorbatova, Rybushkina, & Ivanova, 2016).

Activity based instructional strategy is a successful teaching model in the field of the sciences. Learning activities if based on real-life experience help learners to transform knowledge or information into their personal knowledge, which they can apply in different situations and hence prepare students for future life (Edward, 2015). Activity-Based method introduces some elements of joy, team spirit, respects for each other opinions and reduces abstractness in science concepts (David, 2007). It also helps students to construct mental models that allow for 'higher-order' performance such as applied problem solving and transfer of information and skills (Churchill, 2013). Activity-Based teaching method is in-line with Piagetian tasks as it affords the students a variety of activities and experiences that involve the use of concrete objects. Activity-based strategy hastens the learners' ability to order events through application, knowledge and predict changes.

Activity-Based teaching, if carried out in an effective manner develops skills such as team-working, communication skills, design, leadership, project management, research, problem-solving, reflection and life-long learning in the learners (Khan, Igbal & Osei, 2019). Activity based learning engages students intellectually with the content through adoption of critical thinking, synthesis and analysis, promoting relationship. Activity-based methods help students to move away from basic comprehension and memorization, shift toward active thinking style such as evaluate, analyse, apply and create, which are at the top echelon of the bloom's taxonomy of learning (Edwards 2015). Activity-based instruction in contrast to the traditional instruction changes the focus from delivery of the content by the teacher to active involvement of the students (Kudryashova et al., 2016). In Activity-Based teaching/learning environment, the teacher serves as a facilitator, motivator and a guide, whereas the students are the active investigators of their environment to make sense of the world around them. In this process, the students are bound to experience, understand and master a variety of phenomena.

The shift from teacher-centred method of teaching science to student-centred activity-based instruction encourages and develops in the students the spirit of inquiry and enhance thinking abilities.

Purpose of the Study

The purpose of this study is to evaluate findings of research conducted on the effect of activity-based teaching (ABT) method on learning outcome;

- i) At the primary school level of education
- ii) At the junior secondary school level of education
- iii) At senior secondary school level of education.

Effect of ABT Method on Learning Outcome at the Primary Education Level

Primary education also called elementary education is the first stage of formal education that runs typically from grade 1 to grade 6 (ages from 6 to 12). It is received after kindergarten/nursery education prior to enrolment into secondary school. This level of education lays the foundation for life-long learning. Consequently, research toward enhancement of primary education is important. Coskun, (2018) investigated the impact of activity based learning on sixth grade students'

achievement and attitudes toward mathematics activities in Turkey. Two research questions guided the conduct of this study. The design of the study was a pre-test, post-test quasi-experimental design. The sample of the study consists of seventy-eight (78) students in two branches of 6th grade school in the province of Siirt. Mathematics success test (MST) and mathematics activities attitude scale (MAAS) were the instruments for data collection. Data analysis was carried out using mean, standard deviation and analysis of covariance (ANCOVA). The findings revealed that achievement in both the control and experimental group improved after the intervention. The result also revealed that the attitude of students in the experimental group decreases while that of the control group increases.

Similarly, Suttanon (2019) investigated on using activity based learning to enhance English speaking ability of primary 3 pupils in private Bangkok school. The study was guided by two research questions. A one group pre-test, post-test design was used for this study. The sample of this study consists of thirty-five (35) primary 3 students from a private school in Bangkok. Achievement test and an attitude questionnaire were used for collecting data. The collected were analysed using mean, standard deviation and t-test. The result of the study revealed that there was a significant difference in the pre-test and post test scores of students that learned English using activity based learning. This indicates that activity based learning improved English speaking ability of the students. The findings also showed that students developed positive attitude through each activity.

Kuyale (2019) studied the effectiveness of activity-based teaching method in the English of standard IV. The study was guided by three objectives and two null hypotheses. The study adopted a pre-test, post-test experimental research design. Thirty (30) standard IV of Ganesh English medium school were selected using purposive sampling technique. Achievement test was used for collecting data for the study. Mean and standard deviation were used for answering research questions while t-test was used for testing the null hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. The result revealed that the experimental group taught with activity-based teaching method performed significantly higher than the control group taught with lecture method.

These studies shows that activity-based teaching method could improve learners' academic achievement. However, there is a controversy regards to the effect of activity based method of teaching on learners' attitude. The study by Coskun (2018) shows that attitude of pupils taught mathematics with activity method in the experimental group decreases while the study by Suttanon (2019) discovered that the attitude of pupils taught English speaking ability with activity method increases.

Effect of ABT Method on Learning Outcome at the Junior Secondary Education Level

Junior secondary education also refers to as junior high school is the 7th to 9th grade in the grading system standard attended by students at the ages of 13 to 16. This stage prepares students for writing basic education certificate examination (BECE). On the completion of grade 9, students that successfully pass the BECE are awarded the basic education certificate (BEC). Graduates of junior secondary school are required to pass the BECE to be considered for admission into senior secondary school level. Consequently, studies to investigate for means of improving learning outcomes at the junior education level is desirable. Therefore, Coskun and Eker (2018) studied the effect of teaching activities done by using activity based posters on the students' academic achievement and retention levels in their learning. A pre-test, post-test, control group quasi-experimental design was adopted for the study. The sample of this study consist of sixty (60) students studying at 9th grade in an Anatolian high school in Eski sehri, Turkey. The instrument used for data collection was an achievement test. Mean, standard deviation and t-test were used as tools for data analyses. The result revealed that there was

a significant difference in the performance of English students taught with activity based posters and those taught with lecture method. The significant difference is in favour of the students taught with activity based posters.

Akhtar and Saeed (2017) studied on applying activity-based learning (ABL) in improving quality of teaching at secondary school level in Pakistan. The design of the study was a post-test only control group experimental design. Seventy-six (76) selected using simple random sampling technique from 9th grade students of a public sector girl's high school in Lahore district. An achievement test with thirty (30) multiple choice questions was used for collecting data for the study. Data collected was analysed with descriptive and inferential statistics. Mean and standard deviation was used for answering research questions and t-test was used for testing hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. The result revealed that students taught with the activity based teaching method performed significantly better than the students taught with lecture method. Similarly, Okoro (2019) carried out a study on activity based learning strategies and academic achievement of social studies students in Obio/Akpor local government area, Rivers state. The study was guided by four research questions and their four corresponding null hypotheses. The study adopted a quasi-experimental design. One hundred and eighty (180) junior secondary school (JSS 2) social studies students drawn purposively from three (3) secondary schools in Obio/Akpor local government area constitute the study sample. Social studies achievement test was used for data collection. The reliability index of 0.79 was determined using Pearson product moment correlation. The data collected were analysed with mean, standard deviation, t-test and ANCOVA. Findings reveals that activity based teaching strategies (collaborative, cooperative and problem based learning) improves students' academic achievement in social studies.

Mishra and Yadav (2013) studied the effect of activity based approach on achievement in science of students at elementary stage. This study was carried out in India. The study was guided by two research questions and two null hypotheses. A pre-test, post-test experimental design was adopted in this study. The sample of the study consists of sixty (60) students randomly selected from class 3 students of Shri Kanwartara high school of Khargone district. Science achievement test was used as a tool for data collection. The instrument is made up of forty (40) questions. Data collected was analysed with mean and standard deviation for answering research questions and t-test for testing null hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. The findings of the study showed that there was a significant difference in the performance of science students in the experimental and control group. The students in the experimental group taught science using activity based approach performed significantly better than the students in the control group taught science with lecture method. The findings also revealed that there was a significant difference in the performance of male and female science students taught using activity based approach based on knowledge in favour of the female students.

Khan, Iqbal and Khurshid (2019) investigated the impact of active learning method on students' academic achievement in physics at secondary school level in Pakistan. Two null hypotheses formulated and tested at 0.05 level of significance guided the conduct of the study. A pre-test, post-test control group experimental design was used in this study. The sample of the study consists of eighty (80) students of the 9th grade students randomly selected from government centennial model higher secondary school district Haripur. Physics academic achievement test (PAAT) with reliability index of 0.82 was used as instrument for data collection the instrument consists of 100 multiple choice questions. Mean, standard deviation and t-test were used for data analysis. The result revealed that the experimental group performed better in all the focussed learning levels (knowledge, understanding, application, problem solving, observation and reasoning) as well as an overall academic achievement than the control group.

Sarpong, Atta and Osei (2020) investigated the influence of activity based teaching method used in teaching in social studies on students' retention and academic performance in Ghana. The study was guided by three null hypotheses. Quasi-experimental design was adopted for this study. The sample of the study consists of two hundred (200) junior high school social studies students selected in three (3) selected schools using stratified simple random sampling technique. The instruments used for data collection were questionnaire and achievement test which consists of 40 multiple choice questions. Mean and standard deviation were used for answering research questions, multiple linear regression and t-test were used for testing hypothesis. The result revealed that there was a significant difference in the performance of students in the experimental and control group. Students in the experimental group develop higher order thinking skills, retain concepts more easily, becomes active in class, sustain interest and maximize potentials in performing well. It was found that activity based teaching strategies such as collaborative learning, problem solving learning and cooperative learning significantly affects students' retention positively in social studies.

Mensah (2015) carried out a study on the impact of activity method on teaching integrated science at a selected junior high school. Four research questions guided the conduct of this study. A pre-test, post-test quasi experimental design was adopted for this study. Fifty (50) junior high school in Asokwa sub-metro in the Ampabame number one school participated in the study. Test, observation, questionnaire and interview were used as instruments for data collection. Data collected were analysed using frequency, percentages, mean, standard deviation, and t-test. The findings showed that the performance of students improves after the intervention. This indicates that practical activities improve students understanding of science concepts, observation also revealed that the students were highly excited when using practical activities. Another investigation on science learners by Agbenyeku (2017) studied the impact of activity based method on the performance of selected junior secondary schools in Nigeria. The study was carried out in Katsina state. Three research questions with their corresponding null hypotheses guided the conduct of the study. Quasi-experimental design with pre-test and post-test was used in this study. Three hundred and thirty (330) junior 3 basic science students from three schools randomly selected in the three (3) zones in Katsina metropolis participated in the study. Basic science achievement test (BSAT) was used as an instrument for data collection. The collected data were analysed with mean, standard deviation and t-test. The findings revealed that basic science students taught using activity based teaching strategy performed better than those taught with lecture method. Students taught basic science using activity based teaching strategy have higher retention of concepts than those taught with lecture method.

Noreen and Khan (2019) studied the effect of activity-based teaching and traditional method of teaching on students' achievement in Mathematics at elementary stage. The research design was a quasi-experimental of pre-test, post-test, control group design. Two units of geometry were selected from seventh grade Mathematics for this study. Sixty students of class seventh were selected randomly from the Population of 120 students of seventh grade Govt. Girls High School Bhedian Pattoki, District Kasur, Punjab (Pakistan). Students were randomly divided into two groups (experimental and control) according to the results of pre-test. Both tests were developed from the seventh class Mathematics book for the compilation of data. Tests were administered keeping cognitive domain in view. Selected unit 10 (exercise 10.1 to 10.4 and revision exercise) and unit 12 (12.1 to 12.6 and revision exercise) from seventh class Mathematics book prescribed by Punjab Text Book Board were taught to both groups (experimental and control) for a period of eight weeks. Activities were used for experimental group and the control group was taught traditionally. Independent sample t-test was used for data analyses. It was also concluded that students taught through activity based teaching performed better in post-test.

Evidently, these studies shows that activity based teaching could enhance learners' academic performance and retention at junior secondary level in science and social studies. Furthermore, research findings also revealed that there is a significant difference in the performance of male and female science students taught using activity based approach. That the effect of activity based teaching method on knowledge acquisition favours the female students at the junior secondary school level.

Effect of ABT Method on Learning Outcome at the Senior Secondary Education Level

Senior secondary education is the 10th to 12th grade in the grading system standard attended by students at the ages of 17 to 19. This stage prepares students for writing senior school certificate examination (SSCE). On the completion of 12th grade, students that successfully pass the required subject combination in SSCE qualifies for admission into universities and other tertiary institutions. Therefore, it is important for researchers to find innovative ways of enhancing learning outcomes at the senior secondary education level. With this motive, Alabi (2014) studied the effect of activity based teaching strategy on students 'achievement in chemistry at senior secondary school level. The moderating effects of gender were also being examined. Two null hypotheses tested at 0.05 level of significance guided the study. The study adopted a pre-test, post-test, control group, quasi-experimental research design. Students Chemistry Achievement Test (SCAT) was used for data collection. Data collected was analysed using ANCOVA. Activity based teaching strategy had significant effect on subjects' post-test achievement scores. Students taught with activity based teaching strategy performed better than those taught with modified conventional lecture method. There was no significant difference in the performance of male and female chemistry students.

Amarachi and Vikoo (2019) investigated the effect of activity based instructional strategy on students' performance and retention in Agricultural science in Imo state. Two research questions and two null hypotheses guided the conduct of the study. The research design adopted for this study was a pre-test, post-test quasi-experimental. The sample of this study consists of 118 SS2 students selected from two schools in Owerri zone of Imo state using multistage sampling technique. Agricultural science achievement test (ASAT) and Agricultural science retention test (ASRT) was used for collecting data for the study. The reliability index of 0.82 and 0.84 was determined using Cronbach alpha. Mean, standard deviation and t-test were used for data analysis. Findings shows that there was a significant difference in the mean achievement scores of the agricultural science students taught using activity based instructional strategy and those taught with lecture method. The students taught agricultural science using activity based instructional strategy performed better than those taught with lecture method. It was concluded that activity based teaching strategy was effective in improving students' performance as well as enhances learners' retention of agricultural science concepts.

Khan, Muhammad, Ahmed, Saeed and Aman (2012) carried out a study on the impact of activity based teaching on students' academic achievement in physics at secondary school level. In this study, six null hypotheses were formulated and tested at 0.05 level of significance. The research design adopted for this study was a pre-test, post-test control group experimental design. Fifty (50) science students randomly selected from government secondary school Behzadi chakr kot kohat participated in the study. An instrument used for collecting data was an achievement test consisting of fifty (50) multiple choice questions. Data collected was analysed with mean and standard deviation for answering research questions while independent sample t-test was used for testing the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. Findings of the study reveal that there was no significant difference in the pre-test scores of the experimental and control group. There was no significant difference in the achievement of the students in the experimental and control group in the domain of knowledge

and comprehension. However, there was a significant difference in the achievement of students in the experimental and control group in the domain of application, analysis and syntheses.

Albadi (2019) investigated the impact of activity based learning on students' achievement among 12 grade science and environment students in a public school in Oman, Dubai. The design of the study was a quasi-experimental design with pre-test and post-test. The sample of the study consists of twenty-four (24) twelve grade male students in a public school in Oman. An achievement test and focus group interview were used as tools for data collection. Data collected from the study were analysed using t-test and content analyses technique. The result of the study shows that activity based learning has a positive impact on students learning. The result of the qualitative data shows that students believe that activity based learning enhance understanding, increase a sense of responsibility, create attractive learning environment and increase achievement. Similarly, Anwar (2019) carried out a study on activity based teaching on students' motivation and academic achievement in Pakistan. The study was guided by two research questions with their corresponding null hypotheses. A pre-test, post-test quasi-experimental design was adopted for this study. The sample of the study consists of one hundred and twenty (120) students selected randomly from higher secondary humanities education combination group. Interest test and achievement test were used as an instrument for data collection. T-test was used as a statistical tool for data analysis. The findings of the study shows that there was a significant difference in the achievement scores of the students taught with activity based teaching and those taught with lecture method. Activity based instruction enhances students motivation and improves their academic achievement in education at higher secondary level.

A study by Albadi and Arulraj (2019) on the impact of activity based learning on students' motivation and academic achievement in Dubai adopted a quasi-experimental design with pre-test and post-test. The sample of the study consists of twenty-four male students from 12th grade students in Oman. Achievement test and interview were used as instruments for data collection. The data collected were analysed using t-test for quantitative data and content analysis for qualitative data. The result shows that activity based learning has positive impact on students' achievement. Students believe that activity based learning enhance students understanding, increase a sense of responsibility, create attractive learning environment and increase students achievement.

Ude and Ebuoh (2018) investigated the effect of Biology practical activities on the academic achievements of senior secondary school biology students in Awgu Local Government Area of Enugu State. The study adopted pre-test, post-test non-randomized quasi experimental design. Four research questions and two hypotheses guided the study. One hundred and twenty (120) (60 males and 60 females) senior secondary school biology students were sampled from the population of 490 SS 2 students. Four schools were sampled out of 13 Government Secondary Schools in Awgu L.G.A. Instrument for data collection was Biology Achievement Test (BAT) consisting of 21 multiple-choice test items was constructed. The instrument was validated by three experiments one in measurement and evaluation and two in biology education. The reliability test was done using Kuder-Richardson (K-R20) which gave a reliability index of 0.74. The research questions were answered using mean and standard deviation while hypothesis were tested using t-test. The findings of the study showed that students taught biology using practical activities performed better than their counterparts using conventional method. The result also showed that gender has significant difference on students' performance when taught with practical.

Precisely, studies reviewed at the senior secondary school level shows that the use of activity-based teaching method significantly improves students' academic performance particularly in physics, chemistry, agricultural science, and biology. Furthermore, studies have shown that activity-based teaching method could significantly enhance students' retention of

concepts learned in agricultural sciences. However, it was discovered that there is no significant difference in the academic performance of male and female students when taught chemistry with activity teaching method.

Conclusion

Activity-based teaching method is an ideal instructional approach for transforming learners' real-life experience into knowledge applicable in diverse situation in future life. This approach develops learners' desirable skills especially in project management, team-work, leadership, problem-solving, research and critical thinking for life-long learning. Consequently, activity-based teaching method is found to be more effective than the conventional method in teaching and retention of science subjects, English language and social studies at the primary, junior secondary and senior secondary schools' levels.

Recommendation

It is recommended that educational policy makers, educational administrators and teachers should embrace, support and encourage the use of activity-based teaching method for teaching science subjects at the primary and secondary school levels.

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